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Effect of surface chemistry on the interfacial adhesion of carbon fiber/nylon 6 composites

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#ICCM22

Thermoplastic composites

- Processing environmentally friendly, solvent-free, additives-free
- Recyclability
- Short forming period and fast processing speed
- High toughness and impact resistance

Chassis

Car door

Hub

Engine Bottom Cover

Composites Interface

- Chemical bond
- Vander Waals
- Hydrogen bond
- Electrostatic bond
- Diffusion
- Mechanical

Interface is a critical factor in controlling the mechanical properties of carbon fiber-reinforced composites, and its performance is intensively determined by the states of CF surface.

CF surface modification techniques

The surface of carbon fibers is inert, and the bond strength between carbon fibers and resin matrix is very low.

Experimental

Sample	Treatment Method
Untreated CF	Untreated
CF-COOH	HNO ₃ , 80 °C, 4 h
CF-D ₄₀₀ -2	CF-COOH, 10 g D ₄₀₀ , 2 h
CF-D ₄₀₀ -4	CF- COOH, 20 g D ₄₀₀ , 4 h

Surface chemical characteristics of CFs

FT-IR of CFs

XPS results of CFs

(a): Untreated CF

(b): CF-COOH

(c): CF-D₄₀₀₋₂

(d): CF-D₄₀₀₋₄

Surface morphologies of CFs

(a): Untreated CF (b): CF-COOH

(c): CF-D₄₀₀-2 (d): CF-D₄₀₀-4

Interfacial adhesion between CFs and nylon 6

(a)

(b)

(a): TFB specimen

(b): Transverse section of TFB specimen

TFB strength of CFs/nylon 6

SEM images of transverse section of TFB specimen

(b)

(c)

(d)

(a): Untreated CF

(b): CF-COOH

(c): CF-D₄₀₀-2

(d): CF-D₄₀₀-4

Relation between carboxyl content of CF surface and TFB strength

Positive correlation

COOH content

TFB strength

Treatment method	Results	Reason	First Author
O₃ modification	IFSS increased by 60% compared to that without treatment.	Amount of carboxyl groups o CF surface increased.	Li J
Nitric acid treatment	Improve the interfacial affinity between CF and PA6. ILSS increased by 16% compared to untreated.	Acidic functional groups and roughness increased.	Kim S. Y.
Phenoxy resin-based materials coating	ILSS increased more than 20%.	A chemical reaction between free amines of PA6 and eater functions of phenoxy.	Yi J. W.
A milling process	Interfacial bonding of CF/nylon 6 was efficiently fabricated.	New bonds between N atoms of nylon 6 and C atoms on CFs were formed.	Motozuka S.
Nitric acid and an epoxy macromolecular coupling agent	Interfacial adhesion between CF and nylon 6 was improved significantly.	The epoxy group can react with the functional groups on nylon 6 like amino and imino groups.	Feng N.

(a) Wide XPS spectra of CF-COOH and CF-COOH/nylon 6; (b) element content of CF-COOH; (c) element content of CF-COOH/nylon 6; (d, e) XPS curve fitting of the C1s peak of CF-COOH/nylon 6.

CF-COOH

(a)

CF-D400-4

- ① Chemical bonding
- ② Hydrogen bonds
- ③ Van der Waals force
- ④ Mechanical interlocking

Schematic diagram of the interfacial functionary mechanism associated with CF-COOH and CF-D₄₀₀-4 reinforced nylon 6 composites

Conclusion

- Nitric acid oxidation can increase the carboxyl content of carbon fibers .
- Carboxyl groups on the surface of carbon fibers can significantly improve the interfacial strength of composites.
- Amino groups on the surface of carbon fibers do not improve the interfacial strength of composites.
- Carboxyl groups on carbon fibers may bond with nylon 6 at the interface.
- The way of chemical bonding is uncertain. It may be at the end group or at the carbon chain or carbon-nitrogen bond.

Thanks for your attention!